

A Visual Notation for Web-Based Ontology Modeling

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Abstract. Ontology engineering is key to knowledge representation, but logic-based syntax often challenges domain experts. While visual tools improve accessibility, they lack features like ontology classifiers. This paper presents an extended OWLGrEd-based visual notation with embedded individual views, classifier-based grouping, and RDF 1.2 qualifiers visualization. It provides both formal precision and intuitive design for ontology specialists and domain experts.

Keywords: Ontology visualization · OWL2 · RDF 1.2

1 Introduction

Ontologies form the foundation of knowledge representation by enabling data integration, reasoning, and machine-readable semantics. As they gain use across various domains, accessible design tools become essential, especially for domain experts unfamiliar with formal syntax. Visual methods simplify ontology development by presenting concepts graphically, improving understanding, and supporting collaboration between domain experts unfamiliar with formal syntax and ontology specialists.

Several visual tools and notations support OWL2 [1] ontology modeling. OWLGrEd [2] combines a UML-style diagrammatic notation with Manchester syntax [3] to compactly express OWL2 constructs. Tools like Chowlk [4] focus on structured authoring, while OntoDia [5] and WebVOWL offer simplified graph views for comprehension. However, most tools cover only parts of the modeling lifecycle. Only a few, such as OWLGrEd and WebVOWL, support both import and export. Most lack round-trip workflows and full OWL2 expressivity. Support for RDF 1.2 qualifiers has also not yet been added to the visual notation.

This paper presents a vision for a visual notation for OWL2 ontologies and upcoming RDF 1.2, designed to support ontology development in an online environment. Building on the strengths of OWLGrEd, the notation introduces new elements designed to support ontology developers.

2 OWLGrEd Notation Overview

OWLGrEd [2] provides a UML-style graphical notation for OWL 2 ontologies, combining intuitive visualization with formal precision (see Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Mini University ontology in OWLGrEd notation

Classes are represented as boxes, data properties appear as attributes and object properties as directed associations between classes. Axioms such as *SubClassOf* and *DisjointClasses* are represented either within node compartments or as separate visual constructs. Individuals appear as connected objects, while property characteristics (e.g. *functionality*, *equivalence*) and restrictions (e.g. *some*, *only*) are shown via labeled connectors. The notation handles both named/anonymous classes and supports binary/n-ary logical axioms through lines and connector boxes.

3 Planned Extensions to the Notation

The proposed notation will retain and refine the OWLGrEd notation, extending it with support for ontology classifiers, embedded views of individuals, and RDF 1.2 qualifiers. These enhancements aim to provide more convenient ways of representing individuals and to propose a dedicated notation for property triple qualifiers. We are advancing the implementation of the proposed notation within a web-based visual ontology editor.

3.1 Individual Lists

To improve clarity and reduce the complexity of diagrams, individuals belonging to a class can be embedded directly within the class box.

A class may include a compact list of individuals using URIs or display labels like *studentName(URI)*, derived from a chosen attribute, marked with (*). This provides a lightweight overview for quick reference. For a more detailed view, individuals may be listed in a tabular format within the class box. Each selected property is represented by a short alias (e.g. (L) for *studyLevel*). Individual data is then displayed in rows, with property values marked using their respective aliases (see the class boxes in Figure 2).

<table border="1"> <tr><th style="text-align: center;">Student</th></tr> <tr><td>(*) <i>studentName</i>: string</td></tr> <tr><td>studyLevel: StudyLevel</td></tr> <tr><td>gender: Gender</td></tr> <tr><td>Alice (AL001)</td></tr> <tr><td>Bob (BB002)</td></tr> <tr><td>Clara (CL0003)</td></tr> </table>	Student	(*) <i>studentName</i> : string	studyLevel: StudyLevel	gender: Gender	Alice (AL001)	Bob (BB002)	Clara (CL0003)	<table border="1"> <tr><th style="text-align: center;">Student</th></tr> <tr><td>(*) <i>studentName</i>: string</td></tr> <tr><td>(L) studyLevel: StudyLevel</td></tr> <tr><td>gender: Gender</td></tr> <tr><td>Alice (AL001) (L) Master</td></tr> <tr><td>Bob (BB002) (L) Bachelor</td></tr> <tr><td>Clara (CL0003) (L) Master</td></tr> </table>	Student	(*) <i>studentName</i> : string	(L) studyLevel: StudyLevel	gender: Gender	Alice (AL001) (L) Master	Bob (BB002) (L) Bachelor	Clara (CL0003) (L) Master	<table border="1"> <tr><th style="text-align: center;">Individual list of Student</th></tr> <tr><td>(*) <i>studentName</i></td></tr> <tr><td>(L) <i>studyLevel</i></td></tr> <tr><td>(G) <i>gender</i></td></tr> <tr><td>Alice (AL001) (L) Master (G) Female </td></tr> <tr><td>Bob (BB002) (L) Bachelor (G) Male </td></tr> <tr><td>Clara (CL0003) (L) Master (G) Female </td></tr> </table>	Individual list of Student	(*) <i>studentName</i>	(L) <i>studyLevel</i>	(G) <i>gender</i>	Alice (AL001) (L) Master (G) Female	Bob (BB002) (L) Bachelor (G) Male	Clara (CL0003) (L) Master (G) Female
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Fig. 2. Compact and tabular individual lists

When detailed information about individuals is required, a dedicated list box can be used to display them. This box lists individuals with their property values and any relevant individual-level axioms (see the individual list in Figure 2).

These layouts present the same information and can be used interchangeably, based on user preference or screen layout.

3.2 Classifier-Based Grouping

Classifier-based grouping can help manage large ontologies by reducing visual complexity and improving navigation. Grouping individuals by properties like *studyLevel* simplifies finding relevant instances and identifying patterns, supporting analysis and error detection by domain experts.

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Fig. 3. Classifier-Based grouping of individuals

In OWLGrEd notation, classifiers can be defined using either a *DataType* box for classification by literal values (*Gender* *DataType* in Figure 1) or an *Enumerated Class* box for classification by named individuals (*StudyLevel* *Class* in Figure 1). These classifiers are then used to organize the individuals accordingly. Classifier-based grouping can be applied in the same visual and textual styles as general individual lists, but organized under classifier values (see Figure 3).

3.3 RDF 1.2 support

In data modeling, it is often important to capture not just the facts, but also their context—such as the source, validity period, or confidence. The upcoming RDF 1.2 specification allows qualifiers to be attached directly to triples. Integrating these qualifiers into the visual notation helps present the nuances of the data

model to the end user. The planned notation will display both the base statement and its qualifiers as annotation properties - such as *validFrom* and *confidence* - and annotate reified triples at the instance level using these properties.

Fig. 4. Visualization of RDF 1.2 qualifiers

Object properties are represented graphically as hexagonal blue boxes. These boxes are labeled with the property name and are connected to their subject and object classes or individuals with directed connectors. When RDF 1.2 qualifiers are present, they are included directly within the box using labeled fields (e.g. *validFrom*, *validUntil*, as shown in Figure 4).

Data properties are shown as green hexagonal boxes that are linked to their corresponding subject class or individual. When connected to a class, the box displays the property's *Range* to indicate the expected datatype. When connected to an individual, the actual property value is shown inside the box.

4 Conclusion

The proposed visual notation for OWL2 ontologies and RDF 1.2 qualifiers leverages the strengths of OWLGrEd, including its possibility to be easily extended by new visual primitives. The key enhancements of the new notation include the ability to create compact and detailed individual lists, a classifier-based grouping of individuals, and support for RDF 1.2 qualifiers, all tailored for a modern, collaborative, web-based environment.

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